

The effect of face mask wearing against respiratory tract infections: a pragmatic randomised trial – statistical analysis plan

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NOTE: This document is an addition to the research protocol [1]. This document was published online before the analysis of the data took place.

Working title	The effect of face mask wearing against respiratory tract infections: a pragmatic randomised trial
Date of plan	05 th of June 2023
General information	The analysis will be performed after last participant has completed the trial and cleaning of all data collected. Analysis will be performed by investigators and statistician of the study group.
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Background and overview	
Background	<p>Effective strategies to alter the trajectory of pandemics includes physical measures that break the chain of person-to-person transmission of respiratory viruses. Among the physical measures implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic, wearing face masks in public was widely used in many countries.</p> <p>Two recent meta-analysis of observational evidence supports an association between wearing face masks and protection against viral infection causing COVID-19 and SARS (Relative risk (RR) 0.56, 95% Confidence Interval (CI) 0.40 to 0.79) [2] and COVID-19 (RR 0.47, 95% CI 0.29 to 0.75) [3], but confounding or reverse causality are possible explanation for these findings. Randomised controlled trials are needed to determine the effect of wearing face masks in the public on getting infected with respiratory viruses.</p> <p>Pooled analysis of 12 trials highlight the limited efficacy and limitations of existing face masks interventions [4]. The pooled estimate of wearing face masks in public showed no preventive effects on the risk of influenza-like illness or COVID-19 like illness (RR 0.95, 95% CI 0.84 to 1.09), but the moderate certainty of the evidence hampers drawing firm conclusion. Hence, there is need for large and well-designed RCTs assessing the effects of face masks in public spaces [4].</p> <p>Therefore, the primary aim of this study was to assess the effects of wearing face masks in public over a period of 14-days on self-reported respiratory tract infections among Norwegian citizens.</p>

<p>Aims</p>	<p>The <u>primary aim</u> of this analysis is to determine whether randomisation to wearing face masks when close to others in public for 14-days reduces self-reported respiratory tract infections in Norwegians aged over 18 years compared to controls.</p> <p><u>Secondary aims</u> are to investigate the effect of wearing face masks when close to others in public for 14-days on:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <u>1.</u> Covid-19 cases (self-reported) <u>2.</u> Covid-19 cases (notified from laboratory/clinician) <u>3.</u> Adverse effects of the intervention (self-reported)
<p>Outcomes and instruments</p>	<p>Primary outcome</p> <p><u>Self-reported respiratory tract infections</u></p> <p>The participants will be asked whether they have experienced symptoms of the common cold, influenza, or COVID-19 in the previous 14 days. If answering yes to this question the participants will be asked to indicate whether they experienced any of the following symptoms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Headache - Fever - Blocked or runny nose (airways) - Reduced sense of smell or taste - Reduced appetite - Sore throat (airways) - Cough (airways) - Sneezing (airways) - Body ache or muscle pain - Exhaustion - Heavy breathing (airways) - Stomach pain <p>We define respiratory tract infections as experiencing symptoms of common cold, influenza or COVID-19, and having:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 respiratory symptom (stuffed or runny nose, sore throat, cough, sneezing or heavy breathing) and fever, or • 1 respiratory symptom and at least 2 more symptoms (body ache, muscular pain, fatigue, reduced appetite, stomach pain, headache, and/or loss of smell).

	<p>Secondary outcomes</p> <p><u>Covid-19 cases based on survey data</u></p> <p>Positive cases will be those persons who have answered “Yes” to the survey item “Have you tested positive of COVID-19 in the last two weeks?”. We will analyse and report this outcome using the same model as for the primary outcome.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Numerator: The number of persons who have answered “yes” to “Have you tested positive of COVID-19 in the last two weeks?” during the trial period. - Denominator: Total number of persons who have been tested for COVID-19 <p><u>Covid-19 cases based on registry data</u></p> <p>Positive cases will be those notified to the Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases (MSIS) with a positive PCR-test for covid-19. We will analyse and report this outcome using the same model as for the primary outcome.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Numerator: The number of persons who been notified with COVID-19 to the MSIS database during the trial period. - Denominator: Total number of persons who have been tested for COVID-19 <p><u>Adverse effects of the trial</u></p> <p>We will report whether participants needed any medical attention during the trial or experienced any injuries or adverse effects related to the study participation.</p>
Analysis packages	<p>R version 4.2.2</p> <p>Stata 17.0</p>
Participants and data	
Participants and eligibility	We will include all randomised participants (18 years of age or older) except the participants who withdrew their consent and requested that their data be deleted from our database.
Exposure variable (s)	Randomisation group

Covariates	<p>We will not adjust for any covariates in our main analyses. However, we suspect that age, sex, and COVID-19 vaccination status may be risk factors (e.g., that older individuals will be more likely to have and report respiratory tract infections, and that fully vaccinated individuals will be less likely to have and report respiratory tract infections). We will therefore publish estimates of treatment effect adjusted for these variables as exploratory analyses, following ICH E9 guidance [5].</p>
Data cleaning	<p>If participants have been allocated multiple times, we will include them with their first response and group they were allocated in.</p>
Handling missing data	<p>We aim to prevent the occurrence of missing data. However, if data are missing for more than 5% of the included participants, we will evaluate whether the data are plausibly missing completely at random (MCAR) [6]. If we judge that the data are MCAR, we will perform complete case analysis. Otherwise, we will use multiple imputation by chained equations (MICE), using a sufficiently large number of imputations (e.g., 50). If we perform multiple imputation, we will attempt to model the missingness mechanism and impute the missing data using the variables age, sex, COVID-19 vaccine status, number of children in the household and participants' attitudes towards facemasks.</p>
Maintaining blinding	<p>The statistical code will be written and tested on an imaginary dataset. Testing will include producing all results, tables, and figures as they will appear in the final manuscript.</p> <p>When all data has been collected, a member of the research group will decode the group allocation in the dataset so that there is no relationship between the coded name of the groups and the true intervention allocation. The analysis including the primary outcome will be performed in this blinded setting. The allocation of the groups will not be revealed until all investigators have discussed and interpreted the primary outcome findings.</p> <p>Before unblinding the group allocation, we will publish a short document on Zenodo describing how the results on the primary outcome were interpreted by the project team.</p> <p>Analysis including secondary outcomes, per-protocol analysis and exploratory analysis, will be conducted after unblinding.</p>

Analysis details	
General information	The main analysis will be conducted according to the intention-to-treat principle (ITT) and reported in accordance with the CONSORT guideline for randomised controlled trials.
Main analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participant flow will be shown using a CONSORT diagram. - We will present the baseline characteristics according to randomisation groups. We will check distribution of key variables between the randomisation groups at baseline. The motivation for this assessment is to decide if some variables should be included in potential exploratory analysis (see below). <p>Primary analysis</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - We will report the number and percentage of respiratory infections within each randomisation group. - In the primary ITT analysis of the effect of the policy of wearing face masks on respiratory infections, we will fit a logistic regression [7]. - We will report the odds ratio (OR) and absolute risk differences (RD) with their corresponding 95% CI and p-values. All CIs and p-values will be two sided, where appropriate. We consider p-values below 0.05 statistically significant. <p>Secondary analysis</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For the secondary outcomes, we will fit logistic regression models as with the primary outcome. Using this model, we will report OR and RD with their corresponding 95% CI and p-values. <p>Exploratory analysis</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - We will investigate whether the effect of wearing face masks on respiratory infections is modified by each of the following baseline characteristics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sex (male, female) ○ Age (< 30 years, 31-59 years, > 60 years) ○ Having children (yes, no) ○ Immune status (sum of COVID-19 vaccinations and registered COVID-19 infections) – <i>only relevant for the secondary outcomes</i> ○ Regular use of face masks prior the intervention (< 50% of the time, vs >50% of the time) ○ Attitudes towards whether face masks are preventive against respiratory infections (reduce the risk (1), do not affect the risk (2), or increase the risk (3))

	<p>This will be done by doing subgroup analysis for each variable and we will report p-value and the corresponding 95% CI for the hypothesis of homogeneity of effects for all levels of each variable.</p> <p><i>The motivation for this exploratory analysis interaction and sub-group analysis is to investigate whether variables of interest moderate the effects. We will use the ICEMAN tool to interpret subgroup effects [8].</i></p>
Planned main tables	<p>Table 1. Baseline characteristics according to randomisation group.</p> <p>Table 2. Effect of wearing face masks on respiratory infections, COVID-19 incidence, and prevalence. Numbers of participants in each group, OR and RD (95% CI).</p>

References

1. Solberg, R.B., Fretheim, Atle, Elgersma, Ingeborg H, Fagernes, Mette, Iversen, Bjørn G, Hemkens, Lars G, Rose, Christopher, & Elstrøm, Petter. , *Study protocol: The protective effect of face mask wearing against respiratory tract infections: a pragmatic randomized trial*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7648390>. 2023.
2. Chu, D.K., et al., *Physical distancing, face masks, and eye protection to prevent person-to-person transmission of SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19: a systematic review and meta-analysis*. The Lancet, 2020. **395**(10242): p. 1973-1987.
3. Talic, S., et al., *Effectiveness of public health measures in reducing the incidence of covid-19, SARS-CoV-2 transmission, and covid-19 mortality: systematic review and meta-analysis*. BMJ, 2021. **375**: p. e068302.
4. Jefferson, T., et al., *Physical interventions to interrupt or reduce the spread of respiratory viruses*. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews, 2023(1).
5. Agency, E.M., *ICH Topic E 9: Statistical Principles for Clinical Trials*. EMA/CPMP/ICH/363/96. EMA, 1998. **363**(96).
6. Jakobsen, J.C., et al., *When and how should multiple imputation be used for handling missing data in randomised clinical trials – a practical guide with flowcharts*. BMC Medical Research Methodology, 2017. **17**(1): p. 162.
7. Zou, G., *A modified poisson regression approach to prospective studies with binary data*. Am J Epidemiol, 2004. **159**(7): p. 702-6.
8. Stefan, S., et al., *Development of the Instrument to assess the Credibility of Effect Modification Analyses (ICEMAN) in randomized controlled trials and meta-analyses*. Canadian Medical Association Journal, 2020. **192**(32): p. E901.